

Angelo Leogrande^{1*}°

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

Mortality from Homicides in Europe

It decreased by an average of 67.54% between 2000 and 2020

The indicator measures the standardized death rate for homicide and injury inflicted by another person with the intent to injure or kill by any means. It does not include deaths due to legal interventions or wars. The rate is calculated by dividing the number of people who die because of homicide or assault by the total population. The data are presented as standardized mortality rates, meaning they are adjusted to a standard age distribution to measure mortality rates independent of different age structures of populations. In the following analysis, only countries with a complete historical series in the reference period, i.e. between 2000 and 2020, were considered.

Ranking of European countries by value of homicide fatality rate in Europe in 2020. Latvia takes first place by value of homicides in Europe with a value equal to 3.5 units, followed by Estonia with an amount of 3.19 units, and from Lithuania with a value of 2.47 units. In the middle of the table are Slovenia with a value of 0.73 units, followed by Bulgaria with an amount of 0.72 units and Norway with an amount of 0.63 units. Austria closes the ranking with a value of 0.42 units, followed by Luxembourg with an amount of 0.3 units and Ireland with a value of 0.15 units. On average in 2020 the value of the death rate for homicides in Europe was equal to 1.02.

Ranking of European countries by percentage growth in the value of homicides between 2000 and 2020. Sweden is in first place by value of the percentage growth in the value of homicides between 2000 and 2020 for an amount of 14.55% equal to a value of 0.16 units, followed by Portugal with an amount of -11.11% equal to an amount of -0.1 units and by Slovenia with a value of -33.64% equal to an amount of -0.37 unit. In the middle of the ranking are Finland with a value of -49.62% equal to an amount of -1.29 units, followed by Austria with a value of -58.00% equal to an amount of -0.58 units, and from the Czech Republic with a value of -60.67% equal to an amount of -0.91 units. Estonia closes the ranking with a value equal to -78.59% equal to an amount of -11.71 units, followed by Bulgaria with a value of -80.00% equal to an amount of -2.88 units and from Ireland with a value of -81.25% equal to an amount of -0.65 units.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is presented below. The data show the presence of three different clusters, namely:

- Cluster 1: Spain, Netherlands, Austria, Switzerland, Ireland, Germany, Czech Republic, Sweden, Norway, Greece, Portugal, Luxembourg, Poland, Slovakia;
- Cluster 2: Latvia, Estonia, Lithuania;
- Cluster 3: Bulgaria, Romania, Finland, Hungary.

From the point of view of the median, it results that the following ordering is $C2=3.19 > C3=1.115 > C1=0.59$. From a geographical point of view, the dominance of the Baltic countries is evident, followed by the countries of Eastern Europe and the rest of the European countries.

¹Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.culture@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

Network analysis with Euclidean distance. A network analysis using the Euclidean distance is presented below. Specifically, two different network structures are identified. A simplified network structure and a complex network structure. The complex network structure is made up as follows:

- Austria has a connection with Switzerland for the amount of 0.25 units;
- Switzerland has a connection with Austria worth 0.25 units, and with Germany worth 0.2 units;
- Germany has a connection with Switzerland equal to the amount of 0.2 units.

Conclusions. Mortality from homicides in Europe decreased significantly between 2000 and 2020 going on average from a value of 3.15 units to a value of 1.02 units or a reduction equal to an amount of -2.13 units equal to a value of -67.54%. The reduction in homicides occurred in all countries even if the Baltic countries have a high homicide mortality rate compared to the countries of central and southern Europe. It should be considered that probably the process of integration into the European Union has had a significant role in reducing the mortality from homicides in the Baltic countries. The indicator does not consider the mortality for homicides committed in a war scenario and therefore is not able to consider the mortality connected to the Russo-Ukrainian war. The reduction in mortality could be positively connected to the growth of legality, the reduction of crime, greater efficiency of the police force and the judicial system. However, the reduction in mortality from homicides could also be due to socio-economic phenomena. Growth in per capita income, the ability to receive a medium-high level formal education and to actively participate in the labor market could play a role in reducing mortality from homicides. The reduction in mortality from homicides could also be due to a lack of diffusion of firearms among the European population. In fact, if the firearms market were liberalized in many European countries, we could see an increase in mortality from homicides. Finally, the suppression of the mafia phenomenon of organized crime could also play a role in reducing the mortality rate for homicides. However, it is very probable that this value is destined to further also decrease thanks to the use of technological and IT tools capable of predicting aggressions, such as in the case of feminicides, for example, reducing the overall value of mortality from homicides in Europe.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

